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Distribution of public funding across research topics in Sweden: is this driven by the government funding bodies or the research community?

Qi Wang* and David Minguillo**

*qiwang@kth.se

KTH Library & Division of History of Science, KTH-Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm (Sweden)

**david.minguillo@slu.se

SLU Library, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala (Sweden)

Introduction

The rules and allocation mechanisms of research funding are important topics in science policy studies. Government funding is essential for researchers and academic institutions, allocation mechanisms are then powerful instruments for influencing the direction and performance of research activities (Stephan, 2015). According to a thorough review study on the allocation of research funding, Aagaard and colleagues (2020) indicate that previous literature presents “a rather strong inclination” toward opinions favoring increased dispersal of research funding. But at the same time, they recognize that existing literature is mostly theoretical and builds on opinion-based arguments. To our knowledge, the distribution of research funding has been an ongoing discussion for decades in Sweden, such as the debate regarding the proportion between block grants and project funding (e.g. Ventenskapsrådet, 2017c; Wikgren et al., 2019) as well as the debate over the use of performance-based indicators in funding allocation (e.g. Haake & Silander, 2021; Sörlin, 2007). However as Aagaard et al. (2020) indicate, empirical studies on such issues, especially with the use of Swedish data, are rather few.

The present study aims to understand the allocation of competitive funding in Sweden by exploring the distribution of project funding across research topics and analyzing its relationships with the national research performance.

Data and method

Research in Sweden is funded through various channels like public research foundations, municipalities and regions, non-profit organizations, companies, European Union and abroad agencies. In Sweden, 36% of the entire external research funding is allocated by four public research councils: Swedish Research Council (VR), Formas, Forte, and Vinnova. Two types of data were used to analyze the public research funding organizations in Sweden. One is publication data, which was collected through the KTH Library’s in-house version of Web of Science (WoS) database. Only articles and reviews were published between 1997 and 2021. The other dataset is granted projects extracted from SweCris, which is a database used by national research funders. After several rounds of data cleaning, we were able to identify and exclude granted projects destined to support positions and scholarships, research environment

and infrastructure, networking activities, research visits and conferences. Only research projects awarded by the main four funding bodies between 2008 and 2020 were used in the present study.

The next step was to construct a research topic-based science classification scheme based on the WoS publications and their citation links. In short, a similar strategy to the one used in Leiden Ranking was adopted to establish research topics and which generated 5,053 research topics. To assign collected projects to research topics, we followed the work of Waltman et al. (2020) and first used the part-of-speech tagging algorithm to extract nouns and noun phrases from the titles and abstracts of granted projects. Then a text-based measure of relatedness, BM25, was applied to measure the relatedness between noun phrases of granted projects and keywords of publications present in each research topic.

Preliminary findings

First, regarding the accuracy of the assignment of granted projects to research topics, we randomly selected 100 projects and examined the accuracy of assignments by reviewing the content of granted projects and the research profile of their principal investigators. In doing so, we believed 66 out of 100 projects were assigned appropriately. Meanwhile, we noticed that one of the main issues were related to projects coordinated by private companies and financed by Vinnova. Unfortunately, the abstracts of this type of projects are often uninformative as they tend to emphasize business prospects instead of elaborating on particular technologies, which hinders properly assigning them. Furthermore, those projects have a strong applied nature and research output in form of articles is limited. Therefore, the projects with companies as the coordinating organizations were removed. In the second round of random selection, the precision rate of assignments was slightly over 80%, which we consider acceptable for the following analyses.

Second, the four research funding bodies have distinct missions and are responsible for different research areas (Blomgren, 2003). To evaluate if their different research profiles were reflected by a higher number of funded projects across topics related to their strategical research areas were analyzed. We found significant differences in the topics supported by each funder. Due to limited space, we merely used the data of Forte as an example. Forte's main objective is to promote research in the areas of health, working life and welfare, and it is also commissioned by the government to coordinate research in five areas (children and young people, the elderly, international migration and ethnic relations, disability and social research on alcohol and narcotics). In Figure 1, the base map of research topics was overlaid with the Forte data. The sizes of the nodes are proportional to the number of Forte projects assigned to the corresponding research topics. Based on the labels of the nodes, it can be seen that the research topics supported by Forte include work family conflict, burnout (effort reward imbalance, sickness absence), demography (migration review, ethnic and migration studies), substance abuse, geriatrics, adult care and occupational injuries-related topics such as industrial medicine (occupational exposure) and work related asthma, etc. This suggests that the research topics related to Forte are in line with its mission and areas of activity. Formas also shows similar results.

We further investigated if the four funders show considerable overlaps in their supported research topics. The Spearman's correlation coefficients of VR and the other three funding bodies are 0.15*** (Vinnova), 0.17*** (Formas), and 0.22*** (Forte), respectively. It indicates that the four funding bodies support distinct research areas in practice, which is in line with

each of their governmental missions. In other words, the distribution of Swedish public funding over research topics is rather diverse.

Figure 1: Map of research topics funded by Forte.

Madsen and Aagaard (2020) indicate that research funders may prefer to support the topics “where capacity already exists and where the probability of obtaining results is high” (pp. 1161), and whose statement is underpinned by several studies investigating the data of the National Institute of Health (NIH) (Yao et al. 2015; Gillum et al., 2011) or the U.S. granted projects by Klanvans and Boyack (2017). We examine then the national research production according to the research topic-based classification scheme and compare to what extent the funded research topics can be found in the country's active research areas. However, no correlation was found (0.34***).

We carried out the previous experiments in a higher aggregated level of the science classification system and obtained the same results.

So far our main findings are (1) no considerable overlaps in funded research topics among the government research funding bodies in Sweden, (2) funded research topics seem to be consistent with each funder's mission, (3) no significant correlation between the national research activity, in terms of publications, and the research topics supported by funders.

In the next step, we plan to use the acknowledgment information in publications to examine the relations between public funding and research outcomes. However, we have to explore the correlation relations between research funding and research activity instead of causal relations.

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